

DATA COLLECTION TOOL.

TITLE: ASSESSING KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES AMONG CAREGIVERS OF CHILDREN WITH SICKLE CELL DISEASE (SCD) ATTENDING CHRONIC CARE AT MASAFU GENERAL HOSPITAL, BUSIA DISTRICT EASTERN UGANDA.

STUDY NUMBER..... DATE..... TIME.....

STUDY STAFF INITIALS

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHICS

1. Age group (in completed years)

- 18-35.....
- 36-45.....
- 45-60.....
- Above 60.....

2. Gender

- Male.....
- Female.....

3. Marital Status

- Married.....
- Single.....

4. Highest Level of Education attained.

- Primary.....
- Secondary.....
- Tertiary.....
- None

5. Do you have Biological Children?

- Yes.....
- No.....

6.How many children do you have?.....

7.How many children with SCD do you have?

8.What is your occupation?

- ✓ Health worker.....
- ✓ Agriculturist/farmer.....
- ✓ Engineer.....
- ✓ Teacher.....
- ✓ Businesswoman/man.....
- ✓ Other (specify).....

SECTION B: KNOWLEDGE ON SICKLE CELL DISEASE

1.Have you heard of Sickle cell disease?

- ✓ Yes.....
- ✓ No.....

2.If yes, what was the source of information?

- ✓ community meetings.....
- ✓ Hospital/health center.....
- ✓ TV/radio.....
- ✓ Internet.....
- ✓ Friends and family.....

3.What do you think causes Sickle cell disease?

- ✓ Acquired.....
- ✓ Inherited/familial.....
- ✓ Witchcraft/traditional source.....
- ✓ Don't know.....

4.How do you know that a child has sickle cell disease (SCD)?(Let the study participant list any of these)

- ✓ Getting sick always.....
- ✓ Yellow eyes.....
- ✓ Lacking blood.....

- ✓ Crying excessively....
- ✓ Pain in the legs and hands
- ✓ Eating a lot
- ✓ Not gaining weight
- ✓ Don't know.....

5.How is Sickle cell disease is tested?

- ✓ Blood test.....
- ✓ Urine test.....
- ✓ Scan
- ✓ Don't know.....

6.What can be done to avoid getting sickle cell disease?

- ✓ Genetic counselling.....
- ✓ Don't know...
- ✓ Testing before marriage.....

7.If both parents are sick of sickle cell disease, what are the chances of producing a normal child?

- ✓ None of the children.....
- ✓ All the children.....
- ✓ Half chance of the children.....
- ✓ Quarter chance baby will be normal.....
- ✓ Don't Know.....

8.Is there a cure of SCD?

- ✓ Yes
- ✓ No

9.Which medications are always given to children with SCD?

- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓

10. What worsens the condition of a child with SCD?

- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓
- ✓

SECTION C: PRACTICE AND PERCEPTION OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

1. Have you ever tested for sickle cell disease?

- ✓ Yes
- ✓ No.....

2. If yes did you test before or after marriage?.....

3. Do you know your partners' sickle cell status?

- ✓ Yes.....
- ✓ No.....

4. What would be the reason(s), if you were to test.???or what was the reason(s) for testing?

- ✓
- ✓

5. Did /would knowing your status influence your decision to marry?

- ✓ Yes.....
- ✓ No.....

6. Would you marry someone with SCD?

- ✓ Yes.....
- ✓ No.....

7. Can Someone with SCD work?

- ✓ Yes.....
- ✓ No.....

8.If No, why shouldn't they work?

- ✓
- ✓

AMAKESI: EBITUFU, OHUBASA, OHUYA MUHOLA, OWU L IMU BALABIRILA
ABANA BALINENDE NALUBIRI OHUBAWO BATEGERE ENGERI KYO HU YAMBA MU
ABANA BANO EEH MASAFU GENERAL HOSIPITAL BUSIA DISTRIKITI UGANDA.
E NUMBA..... ENDALO..... SAAWA.....
AMETA

TRANSLATED VERSION-SAMIYA LANGUAGE

EKITUNDU A

1) Oli nende emyaka chinga?

- ✓ 18-35
- ✓ 36-45.....
- ✓ 45- 60.....
- ✓ nhira 60.....

2) Oli

- ✓ Musacha
- ✓ Muhasi.....

3) Oli mudehi/ wa dehya?

- ✓ Ndi mudehi/na dehya.....
- ✓ Haba

4) Wasoma Parka mu sikanda si?

- ✓ Primary.....
- ✓ Secondary.....
- ✓ Univasite.....
- ✓ Sinasoma.....

5) Oli nende abana?

- ✓ Ndi na bana
- ✓ Haba.....

6) Oli nende abana banga?

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7) Hu bana bawo banga abalinende obulwaye bwa nalubiri?

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8) Ohola omulimu si?

- ✓ Musawo.....
- ✓ Mulimi.....
- ✓ Ingginiya
- ✓ Musomesa.....
- ✓ Musubuzi.....
- ✓

EKITUNDU B: Ohumanya hu nalubiri.

1) Owulirangaho hu bulwaye bwa nalubiri?

- ✓ Mbuwulirangaho
- ✓ Haba

2) Niwa buwuliraho wabuwulira ena?

- ✓ Mu hungano che syalo.....
- ✓ Mu dwaliro
- ✓ Hu radio/TV.....
- ✓ Hu internet.....
- ✓ Abecha ne abeho.....

3) Obasa sina esireta obulwaye bwa nalubiri?

- ✓ Ohudirwa bu dirwa.....
- ✓ Ohutumunjibulano.....
- ✓ Eloko
- ✓ Sinmanyire.....

4) Omanyira husi omwana nali nende nalubiri?

- ✓ Alimulwaya lwaya bulisiha.....
- ✓ Ali nende emoni kya Namoki.....
- ✓ Abula mabanga.....
- ✓ Alira muno.....
- ✓ Obuchuni mu mahono nende makulu.....
- ✓ Alya muno.....
- ✓ Ahomera.....,
- ✓ Sinmanyire.....

5) Nalubiri bayi hebera batye?

- ✓ Ba hebera amabanga.....
- ✓ Ba hebera amanyi.....
- ✓ Ba huba esifananyi.....
- ✓ Sinmanyire.....

6) Sina esinyala ohwakamya obulwaye bwa nalubiri?

- ✓ Ohubulirira abadaha ohu dehya no hu deha.....

- ✓ Ohwehebera nimuta dehisanya.....
- ✓ Sinmanyire

7) Abebusi bwombi ni balwaye ne sickle cell balinende ehabi sina yohwibula omwana ali nende nalubiri?

- ✓ Awuma omwana anafune nalubiri.....
- ✓ Boosi banaba nende nalubiri.....
- ✓ Silala syo hubiri banaba nende nalubiri.....
- ✓ Silala syo hune abanaba nende nalubiri.....
- ✓ Sinmanyire
- ✓

8) Iriyo amalesi aka wonya obulwaye bwa nalubiri?

- ✓ Kaliyo.....
- ✓ Sikaliyo.....

9) Malesi sina kababeresanga abana bali nende nalubiri?

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10) Sina esyongera embera yo bulwaye bwa nalubiri olu ba bubi muno?

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EKITUNDU C

1) We heberangaho nalubiri?

- ✓ Na hebera ho.....
- ✓ Haba.....

2) Niwe heberaho, wali no malire ohu deha/ ohu dehya?.....

3) Omanyire abebusi bawo ni bali nende obulwaye bwa nalubiri?

- ✓ Manyire.....
- ✓ Sinmanyire.....

4) Lwasina we hebera/ odaha ohu hebera?

- ✓
- ✓

5) Onyala ohu dehya/ohudehera omundu alinende obulwaye bwa nalubiri?

- ✓ Nyala.....
- ✓ Sinyala.....

7) Omundu wa nalubiri, anayala ohola?

- ✓ Anyala ohola.....
- ✓ Sanyala

8) Oba sanyala, lwasi sa sobola ohola?

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